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An Analysis Of Networking As A Catalyst For Sustainable Community Development

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ABSTRACT

This study examined networking as a catalyst for sustainable community development. The study adopted a survey research design. The population of the study comprised 3,560, this made up of 1,620 CBO Members and 1,940 Government Officials. The sample size was determined using the multi-stage method and a sample size of 356 was obtained. The instrument for data collection was a 28-item self-structured questionnaire titled: Analysis of Networking as a Catalyst for Sustainable Community Development Questionnaire (ANCSCDQ). The instrument was structured on a modified four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagree (D). The instrument was duly validated by three experts. The reliability of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability index of 0.85 was yielded. The direct administration and retrieval of instrument was adopted. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using Z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the findings, among others, revealed that both respondents agreed that networking helps to facilitate collective action and problem-solving, enhances access to education, health and social services, promotes collaboration between local groups, NGOs, and government agencies, increases the participation of marginalized groups, contributes to peacebuilding and conflict resolution in the community. Consequently, the study concluded that it is very obvious that networking plays a crucial role in enhancing sustainable community development. Hence, the study recommended, among others that Government and Policymakers should create explicit policies that encourage and formalize multi-stakeholder cooperation; Infrastructures such as internet, meeting spaces, logistics etc should be provided to facilitate networking, particularly in underserved areas.

Keywords: Community Networking, Sustainable Development, community development, Collaborative Partnerships, Grassroots Mobilization

INTRODUCTION

A community's process of coming together to take collective action and come up with answers to shared issues is known as community development. This participative method prioritizes local capacity building, sustainability, and empowerment. By means of inclusive planning, resource mobilization, and cooperative decision-making, community development projects seek to enhance the social, economic, environmental, and cultural well-being of communities. The sustained enhancement of social, economic, cultural, and environmental circumstances within a community is emphasized, along with empowerment, participation, and capacity building. In line with the United Nations (2016), by encouraging cooperation, inclusion, and shared accountability in meeting local needs, community development helps communities become more self-sufficient.

For community development projects to be successful, cooperation and partnership are essential. Through these strategies, stakeholders including citizens, academic institutions, commercial sector players, government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and community-based organizations (CBOs) can pool their resources, knowledge, and energies in pursuit of common objectives. Successful collaborations promote diversity, establish credibility, and guarantee that development initiatives are durable and pertinent to the context (Brinkerhoff, 2002). The pooling of resources (financial, human, and technical) that frequently surpasses the capabilities of any one actor is one of the main advantages of collaboration. Partners can increase the scope and effectiveness of their initiatives when they collaborate. For example, NGOs offer technical expertise and direct community engagement, while local governments may support policies and infrastructure. Project implementation and sustainability are strengthened by this synergy (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Additionally, partnerships empower local people to be active stakeholders rather than passive beneficiaries and encourage participatory decision-making. The legitimacy and efficacy of development initiatives are increased when collaborative approaches guarantee that they represent the actual needs and priorities of community members (Head, 2007).

Planning and execution that is inclusive also promotes social cohesiveness and lessens the probability of conflict. Partnerships also make it easier to share expertise and innovate. Diverse actors can enhance community development activities by contributing a range of experiences, perspectives, and approaches to problem-solving. Additionally, collaborative networks make it possible to scale and replicate effective approaches across many industries or geographical areas (Bryson et al., 2006). In the end, a community's strength is found in its ability to establish and preserve connections across many levels and sectors, not only in its specific institutions or leaders. As a result, cooperation and partnership are crucial tools for attaining inclusive, successful, and sustainable community development not just merely strategic decisions.

Over the past few decades, networking has gained more and more recognition as a vital component of successful community development. According to Provan and Kenis (2008), networking is the process of establishing and fostering connections between people, groups, or institutions in order to share resources, information, and assistance. These networks support cooperation, resource mobilization, and creativity, especially when tackling intricate socioeconomic issues that call for multisectoral solutions. In the context of community development, networking is the intentional establishment, upkeep, and reinforcement of connections between people, groups, and institutions in order to promote cooperation, communication, and resource sharing in the pursuit of common developmental objectives (Provan & Kenis, 2008). Stakeholders can coordinate activities, improve their ability to solve problems, and foster group ownership of development processes through networking.

By encouraging multi-stakeholder collaboration, knowledge sharing, and resource mobilization, networking is essential to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which were adopted by the UN in 2015, serve as a worldwide roadmap for creating a more equitable, inclusive, and sustainable world by 2030. Successful networking is crucial to achieving these 17 interconnected goals, which call for concerted efforts across industries, disciplines, and geographic borders (United Nations, 2015). SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals, which advocates for reviving international partnerships for sustainable development and bolstering implementation tools, is

one of the clearest acknowledgements of this. It highlights how crucial cross-sectoral cooperation is between governments, commercial industry, civil society, and international organizations. Networks serve as the infrastructure through which these partnerships are built and maintained (Kania & Kramer, 2011). By encouraging information sharing, enabling group advocacy, bolstering capacity building, encouraging inclusivity, and aiding in peacebuilding, networking improves community development. In addition to being interconnected, these roles are essential to making sure that development initiatives are durable, responsive, and participative. A strategic tool for improving community development's efficacy, inclusivity, and sustainability is networking. Networks allow stakeholders to share information, pool resources, and take coordinated action to solve local issues through a variety of formal and informal arrangements. The following are the main functions of networking in community development:

i. Information and Resource Sharing: Networks establish pathways for community players to share resources, experiences, and information. This exchange encourages evidence-based interventions, fosters creativity, and cuts down on redundancy. Networks make it easier for communities to acquire financing possibilities, policy knowledge, and technical assistance by connecting them with NGOs, government organizations, and development specialists (Provan & Kenis, 2008). Agricultural cooperatives, for instance, frequently exchange farming methods and market knowledge across geographical boundaries, improving livelihoods and productivity (Woolcock & Narayan, 2000).

ii. Collective Action and Advocacy: Communities can more successfully campaign for social services, rights, and policy reforms when their collective voice is strengthened through networking. Networks raise community issues and make them more visible in governance spaces through coordinated campaigns, joint statements, and cross-sector coalitions (Bryson et al., 2006). For example, civil society coalitions have played a key role in shaping policies related to gender-based violence, environmental regulation, and land reform in a variety of settings (Brinkerhoff, 2002).

iii. Capacity Building and Empowerment: Mutual learning, mentoring, and skill development between people and organizations are all facilitated by networking. Networks support local empowerment and enhance the human capital required for sustainable development by establishing forums for discussion and peer exchange (Head, 2007). Members of the community are exposed to leadership opportunities, training, and cooperative projects that improve their organizational and problem-solving skills.

iv. Social Inclusion and Equity Promotion: Women, young people, members of ethnic minorities, and people with disabilities are among the marginalized groups that inclusive networks encourage to participate in development processes. They provide forums where a range of opinions can be heard and have an impact on choices (Putnam, 2000). When networks are created fairly, they can assist in breaking down systemic obstacles and promote a feeling of community and shared accountability (Eversole, 2012).

v. Conflict Resolution and Peacebuilding: Networking is essential for preventing and resolving disputes because it fosters communication, understanding, and trust amongst various communities. At the local level, networks can resolve conflicts and maintain peace through community peace committees, interfaith coalitions, and conventional dispute resolution venues. Networks foster coexistence and lower tensions in precarious or post-conflict environments by establishing venues for inclusive participation.

Formal and informal networking can be broadly divided into two categories. Formal networks are organized partnerships that frequently include entities like government agencies, commercial sector stakeholders, community-based organizations (CBOs), and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). Usually, agreements, common goals, and institutional procedures control these networks. They are essential for carrying out major initiatives, influencing legislation, and obtaining outside finance (Kapucu, 2006). Informal networks, on the other hand, are based on interpersonal interactions, shared norms, social ties, and trust between people or members of the community. Although these networks frequently operate without formal regulations or organizational frameworks, they are crucial for community solidarity, grassroots mobilization, and information sharing in local contexts (Woolcock & Narayan, 2000).

Putnam (2000) defines social capital as the "features of social organization such as networks, norms, and social trust that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit." Informal networks help to strengthen social capital. As a result, community-driven development initiatives depend heavily on both

official and informal networks. The purpose of this research is to investigate how these networks serve as tools for fostering collaboration, increasing community capacity, and improving the results of sustainable development. Different kinds of networks have distinct and complementary functions in community development, including resource mobilization, capacity building, inclusion promotion, and long-term change. Although the structure, goals, and formality levels of these networks vary, they all work together to improve development results and community resilience. The following are examples of community-based networks:

i. Grassroots and Informal Networks: Grassroots networks develop naturally throughout communities and are frequently founded on common interests, locality, or identity. These consist of conventional leadership organizations, savings cooperatives, self-help groups, neighborhood associations, and networks based on religion or ethnicity. They are informal in character and usually depend more on social norms, reciprocity, and trust than on formal legal or administrative frameworks (Woolcock & Narayan, 2000). Local mobilization, dispute resolution, and quick response to community needs all depend on grassroots networks, even though they are not formally recognized. They promote local ownership, build social capital, and offer forums for inclusive decision-making (Putnam, 2000).

ii. NGO and Civil Society Collaborations: To solve complicated socioeconomic issues at the local level, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and civil society organizations (CSOs) frequently cooperate through official and informal networks. These partnerships could involve coordinated service delivery, resource pooling, pooled advocacy efforts, or cooperative programming (Brinkerhoff, 2002). These networks decrease effort duplication, boost efficiency and reach, and foster possibilities for reciprocal learning. Additionally, civil society partnerships are essential for promoting policy change, elevating community perspectives, and holding institutions responsible (Banks et al., 2015).

iii. Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): To accomplish development objectives, public-private partnerships entail cooperation between private sector organizations and governmental authorities. These collaborations combine the resources and creativity of the business sector with the ability of the public sector to make policy (Bovaird, 2004). PPPs are frequently utilized in community development domains like agriculture, infrastructure, health, and education. They can increase access to services, foster economic empowerment, and create long-term sustainability when they are inclusively designed. However, if not properly managed, power disparities and profit-driven incentives may restrict the advantages to the community (Bryson et al., 2006).

iv. Digital and Online Community Networks: As technology has developed, digital networks have become increasingly effective instruments for community development. In order to disseminate information, plan actions, and rally support across large geographic areas, these include social media platforms, messaging apps (like WhatsApp groups), online forums, and crowd-sourcing tools (Wellman et al., 2001). Real-time communication, virtual involvement, and the expansion of regional projects to a larger audience are all made possible by digital networks. They are especially helpful in urban environments, with young people, and in times of crisis when in-person communication is scarce (Castells, 2010). To guarantee fair access and influence, however, issues like misinformation and digital disparities must be resolved.

Although networking is crucial for successful community development, it frequently faces a number of structural and practical obstacles. These challenges have the potential to impede cooperation, restrict inclusivity, and jeopardize the long-term viability of development initiatives. The following are the main obstacles that people frequently encounter when networking in community settings:

v. Trust Deficits and Power Imbalances: Stakeholder mistrust is one of the biggest obstacles to successful networking. It is challenging to start or maintain collaborative activities when there is a history of unfulfilled promises, exclusion, or exploitation, especially between communities and outside organizations (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Furthermore, unequal partnerships are frequently the outcome of power imbalances between small communities and large institutions (such as NGOs or government agencies). Disempowerment and disengagement can result from dominant actors controlling resources, setting agendas, or stifling local voices (Brinkerhoff, 2002).

iv. Lack of Communication Infrastructure: The lack of proper communication infrastructure, such as internet access, mobile networks, or transit systems, restricts stakeholders' capacity to interact, exchange information, or plan actions in many rural or marginalized areas (World Bank, 2016). Networks are weakened and silos are formed as a result of this isolation, especially for grassroots organizations that have little access to digital platforms. Furthermore, poor digital literacy and language limitations can make communication breakdowns worse and prevent disadvantaged populations from engaging in meaningful activities.

v. Resource Constraints: Financial, human, and logistical resources are needed for networking activities, which range from setting up meetings and conducting training to managing online platforms and fostering long-term partnerships. According to Banks et al. (2015), community-based organizations frequently lack the steady funding and qualified staff necessary for ongoing networking, especially with institutional or regional actors. Insufficient resources can also encourage rivalry amongst organizations, which deters cooperation and results in dispersed rather than coordinated efforts.

vii. Cultural and Political Barriers: Political interests and cultural conventions can make it difficult for stakeholders to work together. Women, youth, and minorities are among the groups that may not be able to participate in network activities in some areas due to conventional hierarchies or gender norms (Eversole, 2012). Political obstacles such as partisan meddling, bureaucratic opposition, or inconsistent policies can sabotage community collaborations and reduce backing for inclusive networking initiatives. Community-based networking may even be discouraged or viewed as a threat in environments with excessively centralized or authoritarian government. Many community projects function in silos without intentional networking and partnering mechanisms, which results in wasteful spending, disjointed services, and lost chances for collaboration (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

Statement of the Problem

Despite decades of global investment in community development programs, many of these initiatives still struggle with fragmentation and a lack of coordination among important parties. Community-based organizations (CBOs), government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and private entities frequently work independently, pursuing concurrent initiatives with little cooperation or common goal (Banks et al., 2015). This disjointed strategy usually leads to inconsistent results, wasteful use of resources, and duplication of effort, which eventually reduces the potential impact of development initiatives.

The lack of robust, effective networks that can promote cooperation, integration, and accountability amongst members is a significant contributing element to this fragmentation. Opportunities for collaborative planning, information exchange, and resource mobilization are limited by the disconnection of many development players (Provan & Kenis, 2008). Without efficient networking, whether it be institutional, community-based, official, or informal, development initiatives frequently lack coherence, which lessens their applicability to regional requirements and shortens their sustainability over the long run. This lack of cooperation limits chances for resource sharing, innovation, and capacity building as well as undercuts the potential of group action. Furthermore, fragmented approaches frequently fall short of capturing the intricate, interrelated character of community issues that need for multi-stakeholder solutions. In order to close these gaps this study therefore seeks to explore the role of networking in bridging these gaps and enhancing sustainable community development

Purpose of the Study

This study aimed at exploring an analysis of networking as a catalyst for sustainable community development. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the role of networking in community development
2. examine the types and structures of networks that drive development
3. identify challenges and best practices in community networking

Research Questions

In line with the objectives of the study, the following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the roles of networking in community development?

2. What types of networks and structures of networks that drive development?
3. What are the challenges and best practices in community networking?

Hypotheses

In line with the objectives of this study, the following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the roles of networking in community development.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the types of networks and structures of networks that drive development
3. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the challenges and best practices in community networking

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey research design. 3,560 people make up the study's population, which includes 1,620 CBO members and 1,940 government officials. The sample size was determined using the multi-stage method. Firstly, the three senatorial districts serve as the strata from which two strata's was selected using the stratified random sampling technique. In the second stage the purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting three LGAs from each stratum, thirdly, the proportionate sampling technique was adopted in selecting 10% of the population, 162 for CBO Members and 194 Government Officials giving a total sample size of 356 respectively. The instrument for data collection was a 28 items self-structured questionnaire titled: an Analysis of Networking as a Catalyst for Sustainable Community Development Questionnaire (ANCSCDQ). The instrument was structured on a modified four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagree (D). The instrument was duly validated by three experts. Cronbach Alpha was used to assess the instruments' reliability, and the results showed a reliability index of 0.86. The researcher administered and retrieved the instrument directly. To address the study issues, the mean and standard deviation of the obtained data were used to answer research questions, and the z-test statistics at the 0.05 level of significance was adopted to analyze the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the roles of networking in sustainable community development?*

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation on the roles of networking in community development

S/N	ITEMS	CBO Members (N = 162)		Government Officials (N =194)		REMARK
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
1	Networking has improved the sharing of information and resources in my community.	3.00	0.78	2.90	0.75	Agreed
2	Networks in my community help facilitate collective action and problem-solving.	2.90	0.75	2.70	0.72	Agreed
3	Community networks have enhanced access to education, health, or social services.	2.98	0.77	2.98	0.77	Agreed
4	Networking promotes collaboration between local groups, NGOs, and government agencies.	2.93	0.76	3.06	0.79	Agreed
5	Networking activities have increased the participation of marginalized groups (e.g., women, youth).	3.06	0.79	3.10	0.80	Agreed
6.	Networking has contributed to peacebuilding or conflict resolution in my community.	3.29	0.87	3.27	0.86	Strongly Agreed
7.	Community members have not been empowered through skills and knowledge gained via networks.	1.88	0.82	2.23	0.83	Strongly Disagreed

8.	Technology (e.g., WhatsApp, social media) has enhanced networking efforts in my community.	2.93	0.76	3.24	0.85	Agreed
9.	Networking efforts in my community are inclusive and representative of all stakeholders.	3.11	0.80	3.14	0.81	Agreed
10.	I believe networking is essential for sustainable community development	3.09	0.80	3.17	0.82	Agreed
Grand Mean		2.91	0.79	3.10	0.80	Agreed

***key: SA = 3.26-4.00, A = 2.51-3.25, SD =1.76-2.50, D = 1.00-1.75. n =356**

Table 1 above on research question one, revealed that both CBO members and Government Officials agreed on the roles of networking in sustainable community development. With the grand means of 2.91 and 3.10, which are higher than the criterion mean of 2.50, indicate that networking has improved community information and resource sharing, facilitated collective action and problem-solving, improved access to health, education, and social services, encouraged cooperation between local groups, non-governmental organizations, and government agencies, increased the participation of marginalized groups (e.g., women, youth), contributed to community peacebuilding or conflict resolution, and empowered community members through acquired skills and knowledge. Technology (such as social media and WhatsApp) has improved networking efforts, guarantees inclusivity and representation of all stakeholders, and is crucial for Rivers State's sustainable community development, as indicated in table 1 above.

Research Question 2: What types of networks and structures of networks that drive development?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviation on the types of networks and structures of networks that drive development

S/N	ITEMS	CBO Members (N = 162)		Government Officials (N =194)		REMARK
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
1	Grassroots and community-based networks are central to driving local development in my area.	3.20	0.82	3.10	0.80	Agreed
2	Partnerships between government and private sector actors (PPPs) improve service delivery and infrastructure.	3.64	1.01	3.60	0.98	Strongly Agree
3	Community networks have expanded access to education, health, or social services.	3.48	0.94	3.31	0.87	Strongly Agreed
4	NGOs and civil society organizations work effectively together through formal networks to support development.	3.17	0.82	3.10	0.80	Agreed
5	Centralized network structures (with a lead organization managing others) are more efficient in development work.	3.26	0.86	3.26	0.86	Strongly Agreed
6.	Decentralized or flat network structures promote inclusiveness and local ownership in development initiatives.	3.05	0.79	3.09	0.80	Agreed
7.	Institutional networks (e.g., between government agencies or universities) help scale up development innovations.	3.27	0.86	3.44	0.92	Strongly Agreed
8.	Hybrid network structures (with both central coordination and grassroots involvement) are most effective for sustained development.	3.24	0.85	2.93	0.76	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.31	0.87	3.26	0.86	Strongly Agreed

***key: SA = 3.26-4.00, A = 2.51-3.25, SD =1.76-2.50, D = 1.00-1.75. n =356**

Table 2 above on research question two, showed that both CBO members and Government Officials agreed on the types of networks and forms of networks that drive development, With grand means of 3.31 and 3.26 which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50, the answer for research question two suggests that grassroots and community-based networks are crucial to fostering local development, partnerships between government and private sector entities (PPPs) increase service delivery and infrastructure, community networks have expanded access to education, health, and social services, NGOs and civil society organizations work well together through formal networks to assist development, centralized network arrangements (with a lead organization overseeing others) are more efficient in development work, decentralized or flat network structures enhance inclusion and local participation in development projects, Institutional networks (e.g., between government agencies or universities) help scale up development breakthroughs, hybrid network structures (with both central coordination and grassroots involvement) are more beneficial for sustainable growth in Rivers State correspondingly as indicated in table 1 above.

Research Question 3: What are challenges and best practices in community networking?

Table 3: Mean scores and standard deviation on the challenges and best practices in community networking

S/N	ITEMS	CBO Members (N = 162)		Government Officials (N =194)		REMARK
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Mean \bar{x}	SD	
1	Trust issues among stakeholders hinder effective collaboration in community networks.	3.29	0.87	3.27	0.86	Strongly Agreed
2	Power imbalances between organizations and local actors weaken equitable participation in networks	2.90	0.75	3.36	0.78	Agreed
3	Lack of communication infrastructure (e.g., internet, phones, meeting spaces) limits networking efforts.	3.40	0.91	3.09	0.80	Agreed
4	Cultural and political differences often cause conflicts in community networking initiatives.	3.34	0.88	3.61	0.99	Strongly Agreed
5	Regular training and capacity building improve the effectiveness of community networks.	3.20	0.83	3.26	0.86	Agreed
6.	Involving marginalized groups (e.g., women, youth, persons with disabilities) strengthens network outcomes	2.93	0.76	3.09	0.80	Agreed
7.	The use of Technology (e.g., social media, messaging apps) can improved communication and collaboration in networks.	3.22	0.84	2.90	0.85	Agreed
8.	Clearly defined roles and responsibilities contribute to stronger network coordination.	3.15	0.81	2.98	0.77	Agreed
9.	Sustained funding and logistical support are necessary for long-term networking success	3.45	0.92	3.22	0.84	Strongly Agreed
10.	Sharing success stories and lessons learned across networks promotes learning and best practices.	3.10	0.80	3.18	0.82	Agreed
	Grand Mean	3.2	0.84	3.2	0.84	Agreed

*key: SA = 3.26-4.00, A = 2.51-3.25, SD =1.76-2.50, D = 1.00-1.75.

n =356

Table 3 above on study question three, shown that both CBO members and Government Officials agreed on the challenges and best practices in community networking. With grand means of 3.2 and 3.2 which

are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50, the answer for research question three revealed that trust issues among stakeholders hinder effective collaboration in community networks, power imbalances between organizations and local actors weaken equitable participation in networks, lack of communication infrastructure (e.g., internet, phones, meeting spaces) limits networking efforts, cultural and political differences sometimes cause disputes in community networking initiatives, regular training and capacity building boost the efficacy of community networks, involving marginalized populations (e.g., women, adolescents, persons with disabilities) increases network outcomes, the usage of technology (e.g., social media, messaging applications) can increased communication and collaboration in networks, clearly defined roles and duties contribute to improved network coordination, sustained financing and logistical assistance are important for long-term networking success, sharing success stories and lessons gained across networks encourages learning and best practices in Rivers State as shown in table 1 above.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the roles of networking in sustainable community development.

Table 4: Presents the T-test Statistics analysis indicating a significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the roles of networking in community development.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	S.D	SL	DF	T-Cal	T-Crit.	Decision
CBO Members	162	2.91	0.79					
Government Officials	194	3.10	0.80	0.05	354	-0.65	± 1.96	Accepted.

Table 4 above reveals that z-calculated value of -0.65 is smaller than the z-table value of + 1.96 for degree of freedom (354) at 0.05 significant level. This implies that the mean scores of the two respondents on the roles of networking in community development do not differ significantly. Therefore, the alternative is rejected and the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the mean scores of CBO members and government officials on the roles of networking in community development in Rivers State is thus accepted.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the types of networks and structures of networks that drive development

Table 5: Presents the T-test Statistics analysis indicating a significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the types of networks and structures of networks that drive development

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	S.D	SL	DF	Z-cal	Z-tab.	Decision
CBO Members	162	3.31	0.87					
Government Officials	194	3.32	0.86	0.05	354	0.54	± 1.96	Accepted.

Table 5 above shows that the z-calculated value of 0.54 is smaller than the z-table value of ± 1.96 for degree of freedom (354) at 0.05 significant level. This implies that the mean scores of the two respondents on the types of networks and structures of networks that drive development do not differ significantly. Therefore, the alternative is rejected and the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the mean scores of CBO members and government officials on the types of networks and structures of networks that drive development in Rivers State is thus accepted.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the challenges and best practices in community networking

Table 6: Presents the T-test Statistics analysis indicating a significant difference in the mean scores of both respondents on the challenges and best practices in community networking

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	S.D	SL	DF	Z-cal	Z-tab.	Decision
CBO Members	162	3.2	0.84					
Government Officials	194	3.2	0.84	0.05	354	0.089	± 1.96	Accepted.

Table 6 above shows that the z-calculated value of 0.54 is smaller than the z-table value of ± 1.96 for degree of freedom (354) at 0.05 significant level. This implies that the mean scores of the two respondents on the challenges and best practices in community networking do not differ significantly. Therefore, the alternative is rejected and the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the mean scores of CBO members and government officials on the challenges and best practices in community networking in Rivers State is thus accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

According to the results of the first research question on the role of networking in sustainable community development, both government officials and CBO members agreed that networking has improved the community's ability to share resources and information, facilitate collective action and problem-solving, improve access to health, education, and social services, foster collaboration between local groups, NGOs, and government agencies, increase the participation of marginalized groups (such as women and youth), contribute to peacebuilding and conflict resolution in the community, empower community members through acquired skills and knowledge, and ensure that all stakeholders are inclusive and represented. Also, technology (such as social media and WhatsApp) has improved networking efforts, ensures that all stakeholders are represented and inclusive, and is crucial for Rivers State's sustainable community development. Additionally, hypothesis one showed that the mean scores of the two respondents regarding the roles of networking in community development did not differ significantly. The findings above corroborate those of Provan and Kenis (2008), who claimed that networking makes it easier for communities to connect with NGOs, government organizations, and development specialists in order to obtain financing opportunities, policy information, and technical assistance. The study's results also support those of Eversole (2012), who discovered that when networks are created fairly, they can assist in tearing down structural barriers and promoting a feeling of community and shared accountability. The results of the current study also corroborate the findings of Barron et al. (2018), who discovered that community health workers also use networking platforms to gather data and report service shortages.

Research question two's findings on the types of networks and network structures that drive development showed that both government officials and CBO members agreed that community-based and grassroots networks are essential to local development, that partnerships between the government and private sector actors (PPPs) improve infrastructure and service delivery, that community networks have improved access to social, health, and educational services, that NGOs and civil society organizations collaborate effectively through formal networks to support development, that centralized network structures (led by a lead organization) are more efficient in development work, and that decentralized or flat network structures encourage inclusivity and local ownership in development initiatives. Institutional networks, such as those between universities or government agencies, aid in scaling up development breakthroughs. In Rivers State, hybrid network structures that combine grassroots participation and central coordination work best for long-term growth. The second hypothesis showed that the mean scores of the two respondents on the networks and structures of networks that promote development did not differ significantly. This result is consistent with that of Banks et al. (2015), who believe that civil society partnerships are essential for elevating community voices, pushing for legislative changes, and ensuring that institutions are held responsible. Additionally, the study backs up Putnam's (2000) conclusions that

the networks mentioned in the study increase social capital, promote local ownership, and offer forums for participatory decision-making.

According to the results of research question three on challenges and best practices in community networking, government officials and CBO members both agreed that a lack of communication infrastructure (such as phones, the internet, and meeting spaces) limits networking efforts, power imbalances between organizations and local actors erode equitable participation in networks, and trust issues among stakeholders impede effective collaboration in community networks. Disparities in politics and culture can lead to disputes in community networking projects. Cultural and political differences often cause conflicts in community networking initiatives, frequent capacity building and training increase community networks' efficacy. Long-term networking success requires consistent funding and logistical support; sharing success stories and lessons learned across networks fosters learning and best practices; involving marginalized groups (e.g., women, youth, and people with disabilities) improves network outcomes; and using technology (e.g., social media, messaging apps) can improve communication and collaboration in networks. This research confirms the findings of Banks et al. (2015), who pointed out that community-based organizations frequently lack the steady funding and qualified staff needed to network for an extended period of time, especially with institutional or regional actors.

Similarly, the study backs up the World Bank's (2016) assertion that the lack of proper communication infrastructure, like internet access, mobile networks, or transportation systems, restricts the capacity of stakeholders to network, exchange information, or plan actions in many rural or marginalized areas. Similar to this, Ansell and Gash (2008) believe that many community programs function in silos without intentional networking and cooperation structures, which results in wasteful use of funding, fragmented services, and missed potential for synergy.

CONCLUSION

It is clear from the study's results and the discussion that networking is essential to improving sustainable community development because it promotes inclusion, facilitates information sharing, permits collective advocacy, supports capacity building, and aids in peacebuilding. In addition to being interconnected, these roles are essential to making sure that development initiatives are durable, responsive, and participative. Digital networks improve responsiveness and connectivity, PPPs and NGO partnerships bring in outside resources and experience, and grassroots networks serve as the foundation for local development. For community transformation to be comprehensive and long-lasting, it is imperative to identify and incorporate these various network kinds. Although networking has a lot of potential to spur community growth, there are also serious drawbacks which must be addressed to ensure the unlocking of the full benefits potentials. Networks requires addressing trust difficulties, making infrastructure investments, guaranteeing fair participation, and managing cultural-political tensions. Networking initiatives run the risk of being ineffectual or even detrimental if intentional measures are not taken to get beyond these obstacles.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, it was recommended that:

1. To maintain long-term partnerships, Community-Based Organizations (CBOs) and NGOs should engage in leadership development and community facilitation abilities. Additionally, they ought to promote network structures that are inclusive and represent the voices of women, young people, and underrepresented groups.
2. Specifically at the local level, the government and policymakers should create explicit policies that encourage and formalize multi-stakeholder cooperation.
3. To help with networking, especially in underprivileged areas, infrastructure like the internet, meeting rooms, logistics, etc., should be made available.

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